

LANGUAGE PECULIARITIES OF JOURNALISTIC STYLE

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Abstract: This article examines the distinctive linguistic features of journalistic style, focusing on its unique characteristics and their impact on effective communication in media. Through a comprehensive literature review, the study analyzes the lexical, syntactic, and stylistic elements that define journalistic writing.

Keywords: journalistic style, media language, linguistic features, lexical choices, syntactic structures, stylistic devices

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada jurnalistik uslubning o'ziga xos lingvistik xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi, uning o'ziga xos xususiyatlariga va ularning ommaviy axborot vositalarida aloqa samaradorligiga ta'siriga alohida e'tibor beriladi. Adabiyotlarni har tomonlama ko'rib chiqish asosida tadqiqot jurnalistik yozuvni belgilaydigan leksik, sintaktik va stilistik elementlarni tahlil qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: jurnalistik uslub, ommaviy axborot vositalari tili, lingvistik xususiyatlar, leksik tanlov, sintaktik tuzilmalar, uslubiy vositalar

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются отличительные лингвистические особенности журналистского стиля, особое внимание уделяется его уникальным характеристикам и их влиянию на эффективность коммуникации в СМИ. На основе всестороннего обзора литературы в исследовании анализируются лексические, синтаксические и стилистические элементы, которые определяют журналистское письмо.

Ключевые слова: журналистский стиль, язык СМИ, лингвистические особенности, лексический выбор, синтаксические структуры, стилистические приемы

INTRODUCTION

The language of journalism plays a pivotal role in shaping public opinion, disseminating information, and facilitating discourse on various societal issues. As a distinct form of communication, journalistic style exhibits unique linguistic characteristics that set it apart from other forms of writing. This article aims to explore and analyze these language peculiarities, focusing on their functions, evolution, and impact on effective media communication.

Journalistic style has been the subject of extensive research in the fields of linguistics, media studies, and communication [1]. Its importance lies not only in its ability to convey information efficiently but also in its power to influence

public perception and understanding of events. As such, a thorough examination of the linguistic features that define this style is essential for both media practitioners and consumers.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

This study employs a qualitative research approach, primarily focusing on a comprehensive literature review of scholarly works related to journalistic language and style. The research methodology involves the following steps:

Identification of relevant literature: Scholarly articles, books, and studies on journalistic style, media linguistics, and related fields were identified through academic databases and library resources.

Selection criteria: Literature published in Uzbek, Russian, and English languages was prioritized to ensure a diverse perspective. Sources were selected based on their relevance, publication date, and scholarly reputation.

The literature review encompasses works from prominent scholars in the field of media linguistics and journalistic style, providing a diverse range of perspectives on journalistic style across different cultural and linguistic contexts [1].

RESULTS

The literature review revealed several key language peculiarities that characterize journalistic style:

Lexical Features

Use of neologisms and borrowings: Journalistic texts often incorporate new words and foreign terms to reflect current trends and global events [3].

Prevalence of terminological vocabulary: Specialized terms from various fields are frequently used to provide accuracy and authority.

Emphasis on concrete nouns and action verbs: These word choices contribute to the vividness and dynamism of journalistic writing [4].

Utilization of clichés and set phrases: While often criticized, these elements serve to create a sense of familiarity and ease of comprehension for readers.

Syntactic Features

Predominance of simple sentences: Short, declarative sentences are favored for clarity and impact.

Use of inverted sentence structures: This technique helps emphasize key information and maintain reader interest.

Frequent use of nominal phrases: These constructions allow for concise expression of complex ideas [5].

Incorporation of rhetorical questions: This device engages readers and prompts reflection on the topic at hand.

Stylistic Devices

Metaphors and analogies: These figures of speech help explain complex concepts and create vivid imagery.

Irony and sarcasm: Often employed in opinion pieces and editorials to convey criticism or skepticism.

Quotations and reported speech: Direct quotes and paraphrases lend authenticity and multiple perspectives to journalistic texts.

Use of statistical data and numbers: Numerical information adds credibility and concreteness to reporting.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The identified language peculiarities of journalistic style serve several crucial functions in media communication:

The preference for simple sentence structures, concrete nouns, and action verbs contributes to the clarity and accessibility of journalistic texts [6]. This linguistic approach ensures that information is easily understood by a wide audience, regardless of their educational background or familiarity with the subject matter. The use of nominal phrases, inverted sentence structures, and the inverted pyramid format allows journalists to convey large amounts of information efficiently. This conciseness is particularly important in today's fast-paced media environment, where readers often consume news in short bursts [7].

Stylistic devices such as metaphors, rhetorical questions, and irony serve to engage readers on an emotional and intellectual level [8]. These elements can make journalistic texts more memorable and persuasive, potentially influencing public opinion on important issues.

The incorporation of quotations, statistical data, and specialized terminology lends an air of objectivity and credibility to journalistic writing. These features help establish the journalist's authority and the reliability of the information presented. The use of neologisms, borrowings, and culturally specific phrases allows journalistic style to adapt to different linguistic and cultural contexts. This flexibility is evident in the similarities and differences observed in Uzbek, Russian, and English-language journalism.

CONCLUSIONS

This study has identified and analyzed key language peculiarities of journalistic style, highlighting their functions and impact on media communication. The

findings underscore the complex nature of journalistic language, which must balance clarity, conciseness, engagement, and credibility. The research reveals that while certain linguistic features are common across different cultural contexts, there are also notable variations that reflect the unique characteristics of Uzbek, Russian, and English-language journalism. This diversity emphasizes the adaptability of journalistic style to different linguistic and cultural environments. In conclusion, a thorough understanding of the language peculiarities of journalistic style is essential for both media practitioners and consumers. It enables more effective communication, critical analysis of media content, and a deeper appreciation of the role of language in shaping public discourse.

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